

Thoughts on the National Optical Astronomy Observatory

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Astronomy has entered the era of big data, big telescopes, and big surveys. When Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO) was established 60 years ago, the world had not yet entered the computer age, much less the internet age or the space age. Photometers and photographic plates were the prime collectors of photons, often augmented with stripchart readouts or tapes kept by the primary observer. The concept of a National Observatory, with access by anyone with good ideas as adjudicated through a peer-review process, was revolutionary. Astronomers relished the acceptance of an observing proposal for a few nights a semester. No longer would an astronomer need to be at a university with sufficient resources to build its own private observatory. Astronomy became democratized, and therefore discoveries multiplied as never before.

I was a student of the 70s and marveled at Kitt Peak National Observatory and Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) each time I went observing over the next few decades. I admired the sign proclaiming the original member institutions of AURA, the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, which manages the national observatories and consolidated KPNO and CTIO into the National Optical Astronomy Observatory (NOAO) in 1982. The federal share of Gemini Observatory was added to NOAO when Gemini North and South opened in 1999 and 2000. When I became a faculty member, my

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students were delighted to accompany me and join the ranks of mountaintop observers. I was proud this year when my small college consortium became a member institution of AURA.

As we enter a new era in which the 4-meter telescopes of Kitt Peak and Cerro Tololo are merely medium-sized telescopes, and even Gemini will soon be dwarfed by 30-meter-class telescopes, I watch with a tinge of nostalgia as the name NOAO disappears. But the grand scheme to unite the federal ground-based nighttime facilities as integrated operations under NSF's NOIRLab, facilitated by AURA and the National Science Foundation, bodes well for a future that includes a growing system of observatories. NOAO is a founding partner of the LSST, now Vera C. Rubin Observatory, project. NOIRLab, as a matrixed rather than a siloed organization, will help develop synergies that will benefit time-domain science and follow-up spectroscopy of objects discovered through Rubin Observatory surveys. More broadly, it will also facilitate observations complementary to LIGO, ALMA, VLA, HST, JWST, and WFIRST. It will be possible, finally, to develop a ground-based archive that will rival what the successful MAST has done for space data access, through the Community Science and Data Center that is part of NOIRLab. The new structure may one day make it possible to integrate cooperative private observatories into a true US Optical and Infrared System, envisioned decades ago, which ultimately will promote timesharing and foster collaborative research and instrument development for the broad community.

We're not losing our beloved NOAO—we're enhancing its worth through a robust new system that will help facilitate observations, coordinate efforts, and enable data access. I'm excited to witness the reinvention of our national treasures and to continue to reap the benefits from those who had the foresight to make sure the best astronomy was done by opening up the Universe to everyone through open access.